

STYLE OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT: A PRESENT-DAY ANALYSIS

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Introduction

During the 1990s, many schools and universities had begun to phase out traditional forms of educational governance and adopted forms and practices used in private and corporate management. Yet, the meaning and implementation of these changes is contested. Proponents of the new managerialism in education argue that managerial methods are necessary to respond to the demands of a changed environment with dramatically increased degrees of uncertainty in a knowledge dependent society. Opponents view the new managerialism in the context of capitalist corporatism penetrating here to fore sacrosanct boundaries of non- market institutions. The corporate values that academic institutions are being urged to adopt frequently by trustees who come by them quite naturally often fit uncomfortably into the university environment. The traditions of the academy strongly favor individuality, creativity, even heterodoxy. Freedom of action is highly valued. Accountability is viewed as much less important than independence. The introduction of norms that emphasize hierarchy, team loyalty and discipline is difficult, not because they are not worthwhile values, but because these values are not those deemed especially important for scholarship and teaching.

Issues related to Management

A perennial complaint about academic organizations is their near inability to change. But with educational organizations moving closer to the centre of knowledge dependent societies, many administrators and policy makers find that this reactive, foot dragging approach to change is no longer viable. They point out that to control their fate more directly, schools and colleges must become entrepreneurial and move beyond bureaucratic

organizational structures to utilize their members creatively and knowledge more productively.

Yet, attempts to move schools or universities towards a more proactive approach to change, meet with resistance. As the discord between a managerially oriented top management and an academically oriented faculty is becoming more intense, the divisive potential of the current changes can easily lead to unproductive stalemates and worse. The reorientation of universities and schools towards change can be better understood in the context of wider changes in the world of organizations, viewed in this context, it becomes clear that, like all other complex organizations, schools and universities must rapidly improve their ability to position themselves proactively in more differentiated and turbulent environments. To do so, they must adopt new organizational structures and practices and overcome one-sided mental models of an earlier period. As the language used by organizational members increases in variety and specificity, their ability to label, distinguish and identify increases, along with their versatility to framing. A group of seven words for conflict is likely to find it easier to manage internal tension than a group with only one word. But as framing and labeling power increase, we may also lose the sense of connectedness that a lower degree of linguistic differentiation may have carried. To begin with, it emphasizes that certain organizational forms, especially by enhancing our imagination about what management and order in organizations are all about, it has also excluded certain options and issues from views and thus from action. It has enriched our understanding, but it also has impoverished our language and retarded further analytical progress by giving the semblance of explanatory clarity.

A key tenet of organizational theory is that organizations grow larger and more complex, trust and innovation become hard to maintain. Trust, however, is the cement that binds the component parts of an organization and innovation is a prerequisite to prevent organizational ossification. Without trust, organizational communications reduce to commands that get watered down, subverted, or ignored.

Going Beyond Bureaucracy:

The organizational discourse beginning in the 1990s reflects this appreciation that good organizing means balancing inevitable tensions, finding viable compromises rather than ultimate solutions. Concepts and ideas like “organizational learning”, “the entrepreneurial organization”, or “the network organization” reflect an understanding of the need to balance tight and loose, creative and conservative aspects of the organizations. The ideas of network

organization and entrepreneurial organization express similar balance of tension between spontaneous and rational forces of an organization.

Conceptually, networks are positioned halfway between structure and culture. They are patterned, but held together not by central formal authority, but by myriad informal, social, moral and occupational ties. Communities of practice emerge and communicate through network. While a bureaucracy is a communication structure that practices one size fits all, a network organization is a flexible communication structure that changes with the task and project.

Universities are no longer solely accountable to elite power holder, but to a diverse constituency of business professional and political interests. As higher education institutions engage in exchanges with all of these groups, they need to demonstrate efficiency and effectiveness in their use of resources. In addition, they need to respond flexibly to new ideas and opportunities and improve their efficiency in the allocation of resources.

Implementation of Strategy

To implement strategic goals, post-bureaucratic management uses two key tools: allocation of resources based on internal competition, plus contracts and performance reviews. A steadily increasing part of the resources received by individuals and departments in the university is soft money for which they have to compete with other units of the university. This mechanism replaces the traditional bargaining between departments and central administration in which departments typically used the double strategy of promises and threats. While the threats and promises bargaining favoured the strong departments without giving central administration much control over the actual use of funds, the competitive funding mechanism shifts the bargaining power in favour of the central administration, but also opens the door for smaller departments to attract funds.

Institutional Decision-Making Exhibits Several Characteristic Shortcomings

1-Institutional management is management by committee. Committees act much like courts of law. They do not become active unless prompted by outside events. They are good at adjudicating issues that are brought to them, but have a hard time looking into the future and pursuing a self-defined agenda proactively.

2-The operating units under institutional administration is the individual faculty member, not the department.

3-The institutional decision mode aims at finding the smallest common denominator among quasi autonomous individuals , rather than fully reviewing and responding to the challenges of the situation .

4-The norm of institutional decision making is debate to consensus. Since consensus is an extremely demanding decision making standard , committees and departments are known to employ decision making shortcuts.

These shortcomings of traditional decision making have prompted some departments and universities to complement institutional department administration with team based collaboration. In contrast to committees,teams are formed around specific goals and projects,and membership is typically voluntary. Where as committees behave like courts of law,teams behave like platoons. The goal is not to curtail faculty's autonomy, but to increase their ability to engage in collective problem solving and cooperation.

New Demands on Institutional Leadership

1.content ,method and delivery format of a department's teaching are redefined as a department faculty's collective responsibility in light of the pace of knowledge creation and the growing diversity of learners, including adult ,distance and part time students,traditional assumptions about curriculum reviews or so are giving way to system of continuous reviews and renewal.

2 .Using the resources of the new information systems, departments can provide all members with instant access to all relevant administrative data, where as access to such data has previously been limited to a few superiors, information can now be widely shared and continuously updated.

3 .The recruitment of new faculty as well as the selection of new graduate students are two of the most powerful tools a department can use to manage its agenda and culture. The recruitment of doctoral students is hardly less significant than the recruitment of new faculty, as good graduate students can affect the department's culture as much as new assistant professors. This suggests that both recruitment categories be approached strategically and proactively

4.To increase a department's autonomy and to expand its scope of strategic options, many universities are increasing departments discretionary funds to be used as performance incentives, for increased leverage in recruitment efforts, to purchase expert and consulting services, professional development, marketing and physical equipment.

5. Departments must determine how to generate needed resources, how to allocate the scarce resources they have, whether to move into new , emerging markets and a host of other questions.

6. Most academic departments are engaged with a large number of constituents like alumni, business, educational and legal communities , foundations, sponsors, media, local, state and central government. The relations with these constituents must be carefully crafted and nourished, requiring a degree of activism and entrepreneurship that goes well beyond the reach of old style management.

Conclusion

For schools and universities to play a leading role in the shift to a knowledge based society they need to expand and accelerate their capacity for the organizational learning. This requires, first and foremost, the ability to balance the conflicting imperatives of stability and change, central strategic leadership and bottom –up entrepreneurship, individual autonomy, and collective cooperation. The organizational practices and structures needed to accomplish this balancing act certainly differ a good deal from traditional model of a central administration overseeing an array of small academic workshops. It involves the ability to juggle diverse demands, choose wisely among conflicting imperatives and resist the temptation for slogan solutions.

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